

PROFESSIONAL VALUES PRACTICE BY EARLY CHILDHOOD EDUCATION TEACHERS

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 21

Issue 3

Pages: 390-399

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1970

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12585352

Manuscript Accepted: 05-27-2024

Professional Values Practice By Early Childhood Education Teachers

Edna M. Agustin,* Edgar F. Olua

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The study delved on the extent of practice of professional values practiced by early childhood education teachers in Cuyapo District, Nueva Ecija. The study determined the profile of the respondents, their extent of practice of professional values, the significant relationship between the extent of practice of professional values across their profile variables, and the significant difference in the extent of practice of professional values across their profile variables. The descriptive method of research was used in this study. Findings showed that early childhood education teaching is female dominated. Likewise, majority of the early childhood education teachers are in the middle adulthood stage, married, acquired Master's units, holding a Teacher III position, and experienced. Moreover, the early childhood education teachers highly exhibit professional values. In addition, professional commitment of early childhood education teachers is associated with their educational attainment. Lastly, experienced teachers and new teachers differ in the extent of practice of professional commitment. The study recommended that early childhood education teachers may adopt the intervention program crafted by the researcher to strengthen their extent of practice of professional values.

Keywords: *professional values, kindergarten teaching, integrity, trust, respect, professional commitment*

Introduction

Teaching is the noblest profession because it entails giving knowledge to students & inspiring them for higher achievements in life. Aside from classroom preparations, dealing personally with different learners and determining each of the learners' performance through variety of assessments, there are different kinds of activities which teachers have to be engaged in, both curricular and co-curricular activities.

Ballado (2019) describes teaching as a difficult profession. Unlike any other profession, the bulk of work is not only confined in the four corners of the classroom. Notwithstanding the colossal responsibility, teachers are happy and content because they find satisfaction in performing their tasks. Their passion for teaching keeps them working even beyond working hours. They find love for teaching that they consider it more than just a profession but a lifetime commitment. Nevertheless, other teachers are reluctant that they complain when given extra responsibility. Thus, professional values of teachers differ and directly affect their job in the work place. The educational experiences of all are shaped by the values and dispositions of those who work to educate them.

A value is a belief, a mission, or a philosophy that is meaningful (Posner, nd). Whether people are consciously aware of them or not, every person has a core set of personal values. Anyone is motivated in life based on things he/she truly values. Each person is driven to take steps in life in certain horizons. That driving force is determined by the values one advocates.

As Zywoski (2018) mentioned, Values is defined as a set of concepts which mediate between the person's affective orientation and classes of external objects offering similar satisfactions. The term which designates a value is generally descriptive either of the internal state of the person (needs) or the kind of reward or satisfaction available to that internal need. Thus, the concept of a work value of prestige implies that a person has an internal disposition to obtain those external attributes called prestige

Professional values exercise a lasting influence on an individual's career development. Success in achieving a high level of job satisfaction, a sense of self-fulfillment and happy work adjustment depend largely upon the degree of compatibility between one's professional values and the requirements of a working environment.

The professional values of social justice, integrity, trust and respect and a professional commitment are at the core of the Professional Standards. The values are reflected across the Professional Standards and are relevant to all teachers regardless of post.

Social Justice is the view that everyone deserves equal economic, political and social rights and opportunities now and in the future. Trust and Respect are expectations of positive actions that support authentic relationship building and show care for the need and feelings of the people involved and respect for our natural world and its limited resources. Integrity is the practice of being honest and showing a consistent and uncompromising adherence to strong moral and ethical principles and values. Making a professional commitment to learning and learners that is compatible with the aspiration of achieving a sustainable and equitable world embodies what it is to be a teacher in Scotland to shape who teachers are as professionals.

Since values are powerful determinants of human satisfaction and fulfilment, they serve as major influence on the behavior of teachers. Work values of teachers are important for these direct their own methods and techniques in teaching. Thus, professional values of teachers affect the delivery of instruction.

Needless to say, quality education depends so much on teachers. If the teachers' professional values are satisfied, they are more

motivated to teach and become productive. Conversely, the discontentment of teachers with their works affects not only themselves, but also the learners, and eventually the whole education institution as a whole. Teachers who are disappointed with their work may not exert effort to deliver teaching services. Being the facilitator in the classroom, the transfer of learning and the quality of service are affected. The quality of knowledge gained speaks a lot in the life of students for these may form part of their being.

Values of people are evaluated in different perspectives. In a study by Bhuyan et al. (2020) on the value patterns of teachers working in the urban secondary schools in Nagaon District in India, it was found that the highest percentage of the response given by the teachers was found in respect of religious values and the second highest percentage is found in social values. Similarly, lowest percentage is found in theoretical values. From the observation it is assumed that more or less the teachers of urban secondary school values of teachers emanate in the classroom. They reflect who they are as they come in contact with students.

According to Hassan et al. (2018), in order for a nation to develop its fullest potential, the education sector should be the main thrust in molding citizen literacy and character. As such, Hassan's study was focused on emotional health or emotional stability, also called emotional intelligence which aims to identify whether emotional intelligence influences work values among secondary school educators in Malaysia. The seven domains of emotional intelligence being measured in this study are self-awareness, self-regulation, self-motivation, empathy, social skills, maturity and spirituality. Result from the study shows that there are four (4) domains that significantly influence work values among educators: self-motivation, empathy, social skills and spirituality.

Ercan et al. (2019) worked on a study entitled, An Investigation of Teacher Values and Job Satisfaction in Kenya. The study indicated a meaningful relationship between job satisfaction and humanitarian value and power, success, hedonism, excitation, self-control, universality, charitableness, traditionality, and safety sub magnitudes. Another result of the researcher is to regress the teachers' humanitarian values of job satisfaction meaningfully.

A comparative study was administered by Jolideh and Yesgodhara (2018) between Indian and Iranian teachers. The study showed that there is a significant difference between Indian and Iranian teachers in their work values. The differences between the salaries and lack of facilities for a teacher in comparison with other jobs are some of the reasons.

Selvi (2019) conducted a study on teachers' democratic values in primary school candidate teachers in an education faculty in Turkey. Three factors accounted for variance. The first factor, referred to as Rights of Education, the second factor accounted for Solidarity, and the third factor referred to as Freedom. The result runs parallel to the three main principles of democracy which are equality, freedom and justice.

On comparative study of work centrality, job rewards and satisfaction, Mannheim (2019) found out that work-role centrality is a fairly reliable and valid measure: groups of different ethnic origin, educational level, employment status, and occupation differ in their work centrality. It also demonstrated that for each occupational category, work centrality is related to intrinsic, material, social, and hygienic rewards, regardless of the importance assigned to these rewards.

Cennamo and Gardner (2018) investigated differences between three generational groups currently in the workforce (Baby Boomers, Generation X, and Generation Y), in work values, job satisfaction, affective organizational commitment and intentions to leave. The study also seeks to examine generational differences in person organization values fit. Findings showed that the youngest groups placed more importance on status and freedom work values than the oldest group. Baby Boomers reported better person organization values fit with extrinsic values and status values than Generation X and Generation Y but there were no other generational differences in fit. Where individual and organizational values showed poor fit there were reduced job satisfaction and organizational commitment, and increased intentions to turnover across all three generational groups.

Hegney (2016) identified the intrinsic and extrinsic values that were perceived by the members of the Queensland Nurses Union (QNU) in Queensland, Australia, to influence job satisfaction. The results showed that intrinsic and extrinsic work values do impact upon job satisfaction and therefore intention to leave employment. The results also indicated that work stress was high and morale was low and decreasing.

Another study conducted by Valdez (n.d) on the values upheld by the Ilocos region revealed that the most cherished values manifested in the life of the Ilocanos are in the following order: spiritual, economic, political, physical, intellectual, social, and moral. All the seven core values are strongly upheld in the life of the Ilocanos.

Aquino (2021) worked on the Values and Attitudes of Potential Investors in Pangasinan toward Entrepreneurship: Basis for Policy Formulation. The respondents' sets of values toward entrepreneurship are to the greatest extent. They have favorable attitudes toward entrepreneurship. The sets of values and levels of attitudes of the potential investors toward entrepreneurship across their personal attributes, business commodities/entrepreneurial activities and entrepreneurial experiences/operations yielded "no significant differences." The relationship between the potential investor/s personal attributes and sets of values and levels of attitudes were found to be from low to moderate correlations.

In a study conducted by Olua (2014), it determined the instrumental and terminal values and teaching performance of public secondary school teachers in Urdaneta City. The result showed that the exemplified instrumental value of the teachers is "honest" while that of the terminal value is "family security." The average weighted mean teaching performance of the secondary school teachers is very

satisfactory. All instrumental and terminal values are not significantly related to profile variables. The instrumental values “clean” and “intellectual” manifest correlation on the secondary school teachers’ performance while the terminal values “sense of accomplishment”, “social recognition” and “true friendship” also give evident relationship to performance.

Like any other schools, early childhood education teachers in Schools Division Office of Nueva Ecija, Cuyapo District, have their own individual professional values. These varying professional values are put in one umbrella of the academe which amalgamates with the school’s policies and guidelines, work environment and other interrelated school activities. Thus, the mixed blend in the attitude and professional values of teachers may be anticipated and job satisfaction or dissatisfaction may follow. Despite these conflicting and varying professional values teachers, like other public officials and employees, they shall perform and discharge their duties and with highest degree of excellence, professionalism, intelligence and skill. They shall enter public service with utmost devotion and dedication to duty (Republic Act 6713).

When professional values are out of alignment, teachers work towards different goals, with different intentions, and with different outcomes. This can damage work relationships, productivity, job satisfaction, and creative potential. Thus, this was conducted to determine the professional values practiced by early childhood education teachers in SDO Nueva Ecija, Cuyapo District. On knowing their professional values everyone does the right things for the right reasons, and this common purpose and understanding help the teachers build great working relationships in attaining DepEd’s core values which are Maka-Diyos, Maka-Tao and Maka-Bansa.

Research Questions

This study determined the professional values practiced by early childhood education teachers in Cuyapo District, SDO Nueva Ecija. Specifically, it sought answers to the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. civil status;
 - 1.4. educational attainment;
 - 1.5. academic rank; and
 - 1.6. length of service?
2. What is the extent of practice of the professional values of early childhood education teachers along:
 - 2.1. social justice;
 - 2.2. integrity;
 - 2.3. trust;
 - 2.4. respect; and
 - 2.5. professional commitments?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the extent of practice of professional values and profile variables of early childhood education teachers?
4. Is there a significant difference in the extent of practice of professional values of early childhood education teachers across their profile variables?
5. What intervention program can be proposed to enhance the professional values of teachers?

Methodology

Research Design

This study used descriptive-normative survey method of research. Such design was used to determine the professional values practiced by early childhood education teachers in Cuyapo District, SDO of Cuyapo. The purpose of the descriptive-normative research is to determine the normal, typical condition or practice of a given population under study.

Respondents

The subjects of the study were the early childhood education teachers of Cuyapo District, SDO of Nueva Ecija determined through random sampling.

The respondents are broken down into the following:

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>No.</i>	<i>School</i>	<i>Respondents</i>
1	Bambana ES	2
2	Baloy ES	2
3	Bibiclat ES	2
4	Burgos ES	2
5	Cabatuan ES	2

6	Cacapasan ES	2
7	Cabileo ES	2
8	Colosboa ES	2
9	Colimbitin ES	2
10	Curva ES	2
11	Cuyapo East Cetral School	3
12	Manuel Tiaoque ES	2
13	Malineng ES	2
14	Matindeg ES	2
15	Nagcuralan ES	2
16	Nagmisahan ES	1
17	Paitan Norte ES	1
18	Paitan Sur ES	1
19	Sta Clara ES	1
20.	Sta Cruz ES	1
21.	San Juan ES	1
Total		37

Instruments

The main data gathering instrument was a questionnaire survey which was divided into two parts. The first part is a researcher-made instrument which was used to gather data on the profile variables of the respondents. The second part is the list of professional values checklist along social justice, integrity, trust, respect, and professional commitments.

Procedure

To gather data, the researcher asked permission from the Division Superintendent in SDO Nueva Ecija. Permission to administer the survey questionnaires will also be given to the different early childhood education teachers of the public elementary schools. Administration of the survey questionnaires will be personally done by the researcher.

Data Analysis

The data to be gathered were subjected to analysis and interpretation using different statistical tools.

To determine the profile of the respondents, frequency counts and percentage distribution were used.

The extent of practice of the professional values of early childhood education teachers was identified using average weighted mean.

To determine whether there exist a significant relationship between the professional values and profile variables of early childhood education teachers, Chi-square was utilized.

To determine if there exists a significant difference in the extent of practice of professional values of early childhood education teachers across their profile variables, Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) was used as statistical tool.

Results and Discussion

This section interprets, presents, and analyzes the data of the study.

Table 2 presents the profile of the respondents along age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, academic rank, and length of service.

Profile of the Respondents

Age. Table 2 shows that majority of the respondents are 31-45 years old as indicated by a percentage of 54.05. This implies that most of the teachers are in the middle adulthood stage. This is supported by the study of Nolasco (2019) which found out that early childhood education teaching is dominated by teachers who are in the middle adulthood ages. His study also revealed that teachers at this range of age have already their child/children which is/are contributory in handling kindergarten pupils.

Sex. It can be gleaned in the table that all the respondents are female. This implies that early childhood education teaching is female dominated. As emphasized by the findings of the study of Goleman (2019), early childhood education teaching is predominantly female due to several factors. One reason is the perpetuation of gender stereotypes, which have historically associated women with nurturing and caregiving roles, making kindergarten teaching a socially acceptable profession for women.

Civil Status. Table 2 also revealed that 75.68 percent of the respondents are married. This could be corroborated to the findings of this study that majority of the respondents are 31-45 years old. This is associated to the study of Bolen (2020) which found out that majority of those teachers who are in the middle adulthood stage are already married and have children.

Highest Educational Attainment. It can be noted in the table that 54.05 percent of the respondents have Master's Units. This implies that the respondents value the significance of enrolling in graduate studies to further strengthen their pedagogies in teaching early

childhood education pupils. This resonates with studies emphasizing the increasing importance of postgraduate education in today's knowledge-driven economy, where advanced degrees are often essential for career advancement and specialized roles (Mason, 2019).

Academic Rank. It is reflected in Table 2 that 90.9 percent of the respondents are holding a Teacher III position. This denotes that school principals preferred teachers who are holding a higher position. This is supported by the study of Moreno (2019) which revealed that majority of kindergarten teachers are holding Teacher III positions.

Length of Service. It can be gleaned in the table that 86.49 percent of the respondents have been in the teaching profession for 11-15 years. This implies that the respondents are experienced teachers. This is in consonance to the result of the study of Tumbaga (2021) which revealed that school principals preferred teachers who are experienced ones since the very foundation of knowledge in school starts at early childhood education level.

Table 2. *Profile of the Respondent*

Variables		Frequency n=37	Percentage
Age	30 years old and below	6	16.22
	31-45 years old	20	54.05
	46-60 years old	11	29.73
	More than 60 years old	0	0
Sex	Male	0	0
	Female	37	100
Civil Status	Single	8	21.62
	Married	28	75.68
	Widowed	1	2.70
	Separated	0	0
Highest Educational Attainment	Doctor's Degree	0	0
	With Doctor's Units	6	16.22
	Master's Degree	9	24.32
	With Master's Units	20	54.05
	Bachelor's Degree	2	5.41
Academic Rank	Master Teacher II	1	2.70
	Master Teacher I	4	10.81
	Teacher III	32	86.49
	Teacher II	0	0
	Teacher I	0	0
Length of Service as Teacher	Less than 5 years	0	0
	6-10 years	10	27.03
	11-15 years	20	54.05
	More than 15 years	7	18.92

Extent of Practice of the Professional Values of Early Childhood Education Teachers

Table 3 presents the extent of practice of the professional values of early childhood education teachers along social justice.

Table 3. *Extent of Practice of the Professional Values of Early Childhood Education Teachers along Social Justice*

Indicators <i>As a teacher, I...</i>		Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1.	serve as advocate for change	4.55	Highly Practiced
2.	teach students about equity and fairness	4.73	Highly Practiced
3.	incorporate diverse perspectives into my lesson	4.36	Practiced
4.	treat students and colleagues fairly	4.50	Highly Practiced
5.	address instances of discrimination or bias that may occur within the school community	4.59	Highly Practiced
Overall Weighted Mean		4.55	Highly Practiced

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Highly Practiced (HP); 3.50-4.49, Practiced (P); 2.50-3.49, Moderately Practiced (MP); 1.50-2.49, Slightly Practiced (SP); 1.00-1.49, Not Practiced (NP)

It can be noted in Table 3 that the respondents obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.55 denoting a descriptive equivalent of "Highly Practiced" along social justice. This implies that the respondent early childhood education teachers strongly manifest the ability to create a learning environment that practices equality and sense of belongingness among kindergarten learners.

Among the indicators, teaching students about equity and fairness obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.73 denoting a descriptive equivalent of "Highly Practiced". This means that the respondent early childhood education teachers emphasized the importance of equity and fairness to the learners. According to Montero (2020), promoting fairness in the classroom not only gives the teacher respect but also gives the students a sense of safeness and trust within the classroom.

On the other hand, incorporating diverse perspectives into lesson obtained the lowest weighted mean of 4.36 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Practiced”. This signifies that the respondent early childhood education teachers integrate the importance of multiple perspectives in teaching lessons inside the classroom. This supports the study of Beckham (2019) which found out that students gain a more comprehensive understanding of the subject matter when the teacher uses diverse perspectives. It also teaches learners how to use their own strengths and points of view to contribute in a diverse working environment

Table 4 presents the extent of practice of the professional values of early childhood education teachers along integrity.

It can be gleaned in Table 4 that the respondents obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.53 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Highly Practiced” along integrity. This denotes that the respondent early childhood education teachers is leading the classroom by being honest, fair, and doing the right thing.

Table 4. Extent of Practice of the Professional Values of Early Childhood Education Teachers along Integrity

Indicators <i>As a teacher, I...</i>	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. value other people’s time	4.42	Practiced
2. give credit to where is due	4.50	Highly Practiced
3. never take advantage of others	4.55	Highly Practiced
4. apologize if I did something wrong	4.55	Highly Practiced
5. take responsibility to the decisions I made	4.63	Highly Practiced
Overall Weighted Mean	4.53	Highly Practiced

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Highly Practiced (HP); 3.50-4.49, Practiced (P); 2.50-3.49, Moderately Practiced (MP); 1.50-2.49, Slightly Practiced (SP); 1.00-1.49, Not Practiced (NP)

Among the indicators, taking responsibility to the decisions made obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.63 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Highly Practiced”. This means that the respondent early childhood education teachers acknowledge the consequences of their actions, whether they are positive or negative, and learn from them. According to Morales (2020), taking responsibility in the workplace can help improve teachers’ productivity. When teachers take responsibility for their work, they are more likely to prioritize assignments and manage their time effectively. This helps them become more efficient in completing tasks and meeting deadlines.

Meanwhile, valuing other people’s time obtained the lowest weighted mean of 4.42 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Practiced”. This implies that the respondent early childhood education teachers respect the time of other people by being on time whenever there are meetings, events, or activities. The result supports the claim of Tejada (2020) that valuing other people’s time is a sign of respect which is very important in a workplace.

Table 5 which is shown in the next page presents the extent of practice of the professional values of early childhood education teachers along trust.

It is reflected in Table 5 that the respondents obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.54 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Highly Practiced” along trust. This means that the respondent early childhood education teachers exercise honesty in the workplace and refrain from sharing confidential information to colleagues and students.

Among the indicators, returning found items without an expectation of receiving rewards obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.73 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Highly Practiced”. This implies that the respondent early childhood education teachers are selfless and honest. This result is in consonance to the study of Madriaga (2022) which revealed that teachers are one of the most honest, trustworthy, and selfless public servants.

Table 5. Extent of Practice of the Professional Values of Early Childhood Education Teachers along Trust

Indicators <i>As a teacher, I...</i>	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. refrain from sharing secrets and confidential information with my colleagues	4.51	Highly Practiced
2. remain honest with my students and colleagues	4.55	Highly Practiced
3. avoid gossiping about other people	4.36	Practiced
4. keep promises I made	4.55	Highly Practiced
5. return found items without an expectation of receiving rewards	4.73	Highly Practiced
Overall Weighted Mean	4.54	Highly Practiced

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Highly Practiced (HP); 3.50-4.49, Practiced (P); 2.50-3.49, Moderately Practiced (MP); 1.50-2.49, Slightly Practiced (SP); 1.00-1.49, Not Practiced (NP)

On the other hand, avoiding gossiping about other people obtained the lowest weighted mean of 4.36 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Practiced”. This means that the respondent early childhood education teachers promote a positive work culture that discourages gossip and encourages everyone to come from the point of integrity and respect. This result is anchored on the Code of Ethics for Professional Teachers which reiterate that teachers should not gossip; instead, they should talk about subjects that promote collaboration and improve learners’ outcomes.

Table 6 presents the extent of practice of the professional values of early childhood education teachers along respect.

It is shown in Table 6 that the respondents obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.53 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Highly Practiced” along respect. This means that the respondent early childhood education teachers highly demonstrate concern for students, colleagues, parents, and other members of the educational community by valuing and treating them accordingly.

Table 6. *Extent of Practice of the Professional Values of Early Childhood Education Teachers along Respect*

Indicators <i>As a teacher, I...</i>	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. remain polite and courteous	4.51	Highly Practiced
2. respect the rights and freedom of others	4.51	Highly Practiced
3. ask permission before I borrow things	4.44	Practiced
4. solve disagreements peacefully	4.55	Highly Practiced
5. listen to others and respect differences in beliefs and opinions	4.62	Highly Practiced
Overall Weighted Mean	4.53	Highly Practiced

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Highly Practiced (HP); 3.50-4.49, Practiced (P); 2.50-3.49, Moderately Practiced (MP); 1.50-2.49, Slightly Practiced (SP); 1.00-1.49, Not Practiced (NP)

Among the indicators, listening to others and respecting differences in beliefs and opinions obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.53 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Highly Practiced”. This implies that the respondent early childhood education teachers are open-minded by listening to other people’s opinions without imposing own assumptions and biases. According to Beckham (2019), considering multiple perspectives allows teachers to develop a more comprehensive understanding of a situation. It helps them challenge their assumptions, broaden their thinking, and make more informed decisions which is helpful in performing their role as classroom managers.

Meanwhile, asking permission before borrowing things obtained the lowest weighted mean of 4.44 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Practiced”. This denotes that the respondent early childhood education teachers value and respect the ownership of other people. In addition, asking consent demonstrates respect for others’ property and acknowledges their right to make decisions about their belongings.

Table 7 presents the extent of practice of the professional values of early childhood education teachers along professional commitment.

Table 7. *Extent of Practice of the Professional Values of Early Childhood Education Teachers along Professional Commitment*

Indicators <i>As a teacher, I...</i>	Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1. always seek new ideas to contribute to students’ learning	4.57	Highly Practiced
2. attend my classes on time	4.53	Highly Practiced
3. follow code of ethics for professional teachers	4.11	Practiced
4. build good relationships with students and colleagues	4.55	Highly Practiced
5. show passion and enthusiasm for teaching	4.47	Practiced
Overall Weighted Mean	4.45	Practiced

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Highly Practiced (HP); 3.50-4.49, Practiced (P); 2.50-3.49, Moderately Practiced (MP); 1.50-2.49, Slightly Practiced (SP); 1.00-1.49, Not Practiced (NP)

It can be noted in Table 7 that the respondents obtained an overall weighted mean of 4.45 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Practiced” along professional commitment. This implies that the respondent early childhood education teachers continuously improve their attitudes, goals, pedagogies, and perspectives to contribute to the improvement of teaching-learning process and students’ learning outcomes.

Among the indicators, always seeking for new ideas to contribute to students’ learning obtained the highest weighted mean of 4.57 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Highly Practiced”. This means that the respondent early childhood education teachers are innovative and creative. This is in consonance to the study of Goroza (2019) which revealed that kindergarten teachers are innovative teachers. Her study also emphasized the importance of exploring new approaches to teaching and learning that can help kindergarten learners develop critical thinking, problem-solving, and collaboration skills.

Table 8 presents the summary of the extent of practice of the professional values of early childhood education teachers.

Table 8. *Summary of the Extent of Practice of the Professional Values of Early Childhood Education Teachers*

Indicators	Overall Weighted Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
Social Justice	4.55	Highly Practiced
Integrity	4.53	Highly Practiced
Trust	4.54	Highly Practiced
Respect	4.53	Highly Practiced
Professional Commitments	4.45	Practiced
Grand Weighted Mean	4.52	Highly Practiced

Legend: 4.50-5.00, Highly Practiced (HP); 3.50-4.49, Practiced (P); 2.50-3.49, Moderately Practiced (MP); 1.50-2.49, Slightly Practiced (SP); 1.00-1.49, Not Practiced (NP)

It is reflected in Table 8 that the respondents obtained a grand weighted mean of 4.52 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Highly

Practiced”. This signifies that the respondent early childhood education teachers highly manifest professional values. Among the indicators, social justice obtained the highest overall weighted mean of 4.55 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Highly Practiced” while professional commitments obtained the lowest overall weighted mean of 4.45 denoting a descriptive equivalent of “Practiced”.

Significant Relationship between the Professional Values and Profile Variables of Early Childhood Education Teachers

Table 9 which is shown in the next page presents the significant relationship between the professional values and profile variables of early childhood education teachers.

Table 9. Significant Relationship between the Professional Values and Profile of the Respondents

Profile	Extent of Professional Values Practiced by ECE Teachers				
	Social Justice	Integrity	Trust	Respect	Professional Commitment
Age	.243	.352	.482	.382	.301
Sex	.562	.518	.591	.547	.488
Civil Status	.472	.264	.329	.338	.471
Highest Educational Attainment	.374	.225	.313	.332	.000*
Academic Rank	.432	.642	.586	.412	.487
Length of Service as Teacher	.625	.408	.403	.116	.350

Note: * significant at 5% alpha

It can be gleaned in Table 9 that there is significant relationship between the highest educational attainment and professional commitment as indicated by the computed significance value of .000 which is less than the set level of significance which is .05. This implies that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between the highest educational attainment and professional commitment is rejected. The result is in consonance to the study of Cennamo and Gardner (2018) which found out that educational attainment is correlated with teachers' level of professional commitment. His study revealed that professionally committed teachers enroll in graduate studies to further enhance their strategies and pedagogies in teaching.

Significant Difference in the Extent of Practice of Professional Values of Early Childhood Education Teachers across their Profile Variables

Table 10 which is shown in the next page presents the significant difference in the extent of practice of professional values of early childhood education teachers across their profile variables.

Table 10. Significant Difference in the Extent of Practice of Professional Values across Profile of the Respondents

Profile	Extent of Practice of Professional Values				
	Social Justice	Integrity	Trust	Respect	Professional Commitment
Age	.229	.381	.304	.219	.483
Sex	.337	.472	.448	.298	.422
Civil Status	.423	.449	.362	.771	.382
Highest Educational Attainment	.533	.531	.489	.443	.276
Academic Rank	.337	.538	.552	.287	.099
Length of Service as Teacher	.114	.265	.226	.096	.000*

Note: * significant at 5% alpha

It can be noted in Table 10 that there is significant difference in the extent of practice of the professional commitment of the respondents across their length of service as indicated by the significance value of .000 which is less than the set level of significance which is .05. This implies that the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference in the extent of practice of the professional commitment of the respondents across their length of service is rejected. Likewise, the significant difference lies between kindergarten teachers who are in the service for less than 5 years and those who are in the service for more than 15 years (See Appendix F). The result is in consonance to the study of Gab (2019) which found out that length of service affects the commitment of teachers in performing their roles as classroom managers. His study also pointed out that teachers who are experienced are more committed to service than those who are new in the workplace.

Intervention Program to Enhance the Extent of Practice of Professional Values of Early Childhood Education Teachers

Based on the salient findings of the study, the researcher crafted intervention program to enhance the extent of practice of the professional values of early childhood education teachers. The indicators with least weighted mean were considered in the crafting of the intervention program.

Along social justice, the indicator with the least weighted mean is incorporating diverse perspectives into lesson. The activities proposed by the researcher is to conduct Learning Action Cell (LAC) Session on incorporating diverse perspectives into lesson and Focus Group Discussion (FGD) focusing on ways on how to incorporate diverse perspectives into lesson.

In terms of integrity, valuing other people's time obtained the least weighted mean. The researcher proposed activities under this indicator such as conduct of Focus Group Discussion (FGD) on how to increase sense of valuing other people's time, arriving on time for meetings/ appointments, and getting rid of distractions during conversations.

Meanwhile, avoiding gossiping about other people obtained the least weighted mean along trust. The activities proposed by the researcher under this indicator include conduct of Focus Group Discussion (FGD) on how to avoid gossiping about other people, establishing and maintaining professional relationships at the workplace, and being honest and having an open communication with colleagues.

Along respect, asking permission before borrowing things obtained the lowest weighted mean. Also, the researcher proposed activities under this indicator such as conduct of Focus Group Discussion (FGD) on strengthening the value of asking permission before borrowing things.

Lastly, following code of ethics for professional teachers obtained the least weighted mean along professional commitment. In order to improve this indicator, the researcher proposed activity such as conduct of Learning Action Cell (LAC) Session which revisits the code of ethics for professional teachers.

Conclusions

Early childhood education teaching is female-dominated, with the majority of kindergarten teachers being in the middle adulthood stage, married, having acquired Master's units, holding a Teacher III position, and being experienced. These teachers highly exhibit professional values, and their professional commitment is associated with their educational attainment. There is a noticeable difference in the extent of practice of professional commitment between experienced and new teachers. Early childhood education teachers may adopt the intervention program crafted by the researcher to strengthen their practice of professional values. Additionally, a similar study should be conducted considering other factors that can affect the extent of practice of professional values among early childhood education teachers. More relevant training should be provided to further strengthen the practice of professional values. Future researchers could utilize the results of this study for their references.

References

- Aquino, F. (2021). *Core Values of Professional Teachers*. Manila: National Bookstore.
- Ballado, E. (2019). *Research Methods: Principles and Application*. Manila: Rex Publication.
- Beckham, A. (2019). The Relationship between Values and Job Satisfaction of Teachers in Elementary and Secondary Schools. *Educational Policy Analysis and Strategic Research*, 13, 54-70. 10.29329/epasr.2018.137.3.
- Bhuyan, L. (2020). *Managing People by Filipino Values*. Manila: Our Lady of Manaoag Publishers.
- Cennamo, L. & Gardner, R. (2018). *Education for Values: Morals, Ethics and Citizenship in Contemporary Teaching*. London: Kogan Page Limited. ISBN 0 7494 3065 6 p. 150.
- Ercan, D. (2019). Moral-Character Development for Teacher Education. *Action in Teacher Education*, 38(3), 194-206. DOI: 10.1080/01626620.2016.1194785.
- Gab, L.G. (2019). A study of the relationship between elementary principal leadership behavior and teacher values. *Dissertation Abstracts International*, 54 (7-8) 2201.
- Goroza, L. (2019). How to Improve Teacher-Teacher Relationships. *The Elementary School Journal*. Retrieved January 29, 2019 from www.jstor.org.
- Hassan, C.R. (2018). *Freedom to Learn: A View of What Education Might Become*. Columbus Ohio: Charles E. Merrill Publishing Company.
- Hegney, R., (2016). Exploring UK secondary teachers' professional values: an overview of the literature since 2000. *Educational research*, 52(4), 409-425.
- Jolideh, L. & Yesgodhara, G. (2018). 15 Values and ideals in teachers' professional judgement. *Changing teacher professionalism: International trends, challenges and ways forward*, 184.
- Madriaga, Z. (2022). Evaluation of Life Values of Candidate Teachers of Physical Education in Terms of Gender, Class and Playing Sports. Retrieved February 9, 2022 at www.idosi.org.
- Mannheim, S. (2019). *Predicting Teacher Values on Work Performance, Social Support, and Career Success [PDF]*.
- Montero, M. (2020). Values Development: Tool in Molding the Academic Performance of Grade School Pupils of Lourdes Elementary School, Lourdes Buhi Camarines Sur. *First International Research Conference on K-12 Education, Journal* (August 22, 2020).
- Morales, M. (20202). Values Development: Tool in Molding the Academic Performance Of Grade Four Pupils At Santiago Integrated School, Santiago, Iriga City. *First International Research Conference on K-12 Education, Journal*.
- Olua, E. (2014). *Values of High School Students in Urdaneta City*. Masterate, Pangasinan State University.

Posner, K. (n.d). Those who can teach.10th Ed. New York: Houghton Mifflin

Republic Act No. 6713. An Act Establishing a Code of Conduct and Ethical Standards For Public Officials and Employees.

Selvi, M. (2019). Fostering Teacher Professionalism in Schools. The Role of Leadership Orientation and Trust. Educational Administration Quarterly, 45(2), 217-247. DOI: 10.1177/0013161X08330501

Tejada, B. (2020). Values Upheld by the Ilocanos in Ilocos Region. A publication of the Research and Educational Development Training Institute. Volume 6, ISSN 166.

Valdez, B. (nd). A Study on Value Pattern of Teachers Working in Urban Secondary school of Nagaon District.

Zywoski, J. F. (2018) The morale and teaching effectiveness of junior college teachers. (Eric Document Reproduction Service No. 134 266).

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Edna M. Agustin

Urduaneta City University – Philippines

Dr. Edgar F. Olua

Urduaneta City University – Philippines